

AI Methods for Digital Twins

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The interTwin project is focused on creating a prototype of a digital twin engine. This engine is designed based on a blueprint architecture that follows open standards and promotes interoperability. The main objective is to establish a common approach for implementing digital twins across various scientific applications and disciplines, fostering collaboration among developers.

The project encompasses several use-cases, including high-energy physics, radioastronomy, Astroparticle physics, climate research, and environmental monitoring. These applications have complex requirements that are expected to push the boundaries of modelling and simulation. This will involve tasks such as workflow composition, data management and processing, quality and uncertainty tracing of models, data fusion, and analytics.

To validate the technology, multiple infrastructure facilities will be utilized, enhancing user accessibility to technological capabilities and supporting the integration of Artificial Intelligence methods in research. The main task for the student is to focus on developing AI/ML tools for Digital Twins. This involves improving the student's Python skills and gaining knowledge in distributed computing.

Overall, the interTwin project offers an exciting opportunity to contribute to cutting-edge research and gain valuable experience in the field of digital twins and AI/ML.

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I really appreciate the great atmosphere of the group; the tennis evenings were always funny so I hope that we will meet and play again.

ABSTRACT

This report explores the concept of Digital Twins (DT) and their relevance in the realm of machine learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The focus is on the interTwin project at CERN openlab, which seeks to develop a framework called the Digital Twin Engine (DTE). The framework is designed with a flexible architecture capable of supporting various use-cases. This report provides an overview of the different modules and tasks involved in its implementation.

One crucial aspect discussed is the significance of distributed computing infrastructure in facilitating efficient model training. Additionally, the report addresses the challenges associated with integrating different machine learning frameworks. It also delves into the implementation details for AI methods, including pipelining and distribution techniques, which offer modularity and flexibility for the end-users.

Moreover, the report covers the inclusion of parameter search using framework like Ray. This technique enables the discovery of an optimal set of parameters to achieve the best possible results in a parameter space through a distributed approach.

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1. Introduction

Machine learning nowadays attracts a lot of attention due to its impressive results in a wide variety of industries and scientific fields. One problem is most models require of lots of data, which is time consuming and expensive to collect. One of the solutions is to introduce Digital Twin (DT), which is a digital copy of the environment, that emulates the process or object in detail. Using DTs, we can then emulate the environment and use it for further development, including data collection and model development which is then tested in this digital environment.

One of the projects at CERN openlab is the interTwin project, which aims to develop an interdisciplinary Digital Twin Engine (DTE). To achieve this, many different problems and tasks need to be tackled, some of them include workflow composition, data management together with data analysis and efficient, distributed execution of the applications. Many use-cases are involved from sciences such as High-Energy Physics, radioastronomy, climate forecasting and environmental monitoring. Those sciences can use the general architecture of the DTE framework and flexibly and easily develop their DTs.

The complexity of this task requires the collaboration of many institutions that work together in work packages, such as DT Applications, Thematic Modules and Core Modules together with providing infrastructure as can be seen in Figure 1. These modules are further divided into smaller tasks. The Core Module includes Quality Verification, Workflow composition, Data Fusion, AI/ML together with Real time data acquisition and processing.

Figure 1: Illustration of separation of the interTwin project into different modules [interTwin, [link](#)]

The scope of this internship was within the AI/ML task, which is responsible for the development of the AI backend that enables the users to develop their applications effectively in a distributed fashion. One of the goals is to abstract the intricacy of the different frameworks that are nowadays used for ML (TensorFlow, PyTorch) development and provide users with the simple, yet efficient way of working with ML models without directly interacting with different frameworks. One of the requirements for achieving efficiently trained ML models is the distribution to computing infrastructure.

Due to the extensive collaboration between different research institution, computing centres and universities, as can be seen in Figure 2, one key challenge is the unification of the computing infrastructure. The goal is to enable communication and interoperability between High Performance Computing (HPC), High Throughput Computing (HTC) and cloud resource providers.

In this report, the design and implementation details of the AI methods are discussed and explained. A general description together with implementation information is provided in each section. Starting from the

section *Digital Twins & Artificial Intelligence*, which connects these two fields and outlines the general tasks to solve during development. The next section, *Pipelining*, introduces pipelines as a necessary step for the efficient execution of the application. Next, the *Distribution* of the processes in order to improve efficiency of the pipelines is explained. Finally, *Parameter Search* to explore optimal solutions is described and general remarks towards future are provided. Future directions are provided together with analysis of simple results on first models.

Figure 2: Resource providers and collaborators for the interTwin project [interTwin, [link](#)]

2. Digital Twins & Artificial Intelligence

Digital Twin is a concept that involves creating a digital representation of a real-world object or an environment. While this definition may seem abstract, it can be better understood through an example. Let's consider the example of Google Maps, which can be seen as a digital twin of the real world.

Suppose a user wants to navigate to a particular destination. They update their GPS location on Google Maps, which then receives this information. Internally, Google Maps may utilize various simulations, such as traffic jam simulations, to accurately predict and suggest the most optimal routes. The best routes are then presented to the user, who can decide which path to take. The user then updates their location again, continuing this cycle as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Illustration of the interaction between Digital Twin and its real-world physical twin.

For those familiar with reinforcement learning, this concept bears resemblance to the interaction between an agent (user) and environment (digital twin). However, our focus here is not on updating agent behaviour, but rather on accurately describing the environment using a digital twin. The idea of representing the environment and its processes with machine learning models is preferred, as recent advances in deep learning have shown their effectiveness across various tasks.

In our case, we aim to train, test, and validate user-developed models for specific applications or use-cases. The challenge lies in the heterogeneity of platforms and frameworks available for model development. Currently, TensorFlow and PyTorch are the most used libraries in Python, making it natural to support them in the digital twin. However, their syntax and approach to model creation and training differ.

To address this, it is desirable to unify both frameworks under the hood through configuration files, which can save users' significant time. Given the wide range of use-cases and applications for digital twins (such as Radio Astronomy, Cyclone Detection, and Climate Research, as shown in Figure 4), there is a need for abstraction and modularity. It should be easy to integrate and run new use-cases in a distributed manner. As the project is still in its early stages, the current state lacked the necessary abstraction and modularity. To address this, we introduced general interfaces and components to facilitate easier integration of use-cases. For running components sequentially, pipelines were introduced.

Figure 4: Examples of use-cases for digital twins

Neural networks are widely used models in machine learning, but they have a major drawback - they require a large amount of data. This poses a challenge when it comes to training them. How can we effectively train our models when we must handle thousands of gigabytes of data? This is where distributed computing comes into play. Distributed computing focuses on running programs and algorithms in parallel and distributed fashion. In the case of training neural networks, it means that the training process should be done in a distributed manner. This approach helps reduce memory consumption per computer and allows for faster training times.

When I joined the project, it was in an experimental stage with various approaches being explored to solve the problems at hand. Most of the use-cases relied on a Command Line Interface (CLI), including a classifier created using neural networks on the MNIST dataset for testing purposes. Workflows were provided to ensure that all required packages were installed and that an isolated environment was used for running each specific use-case. Logging was also implemented, specifically using MLFlow, but there was a need to introduce additional logging methods.

For the reasons mentioned above, I decided to start by abstracting the existing trainers and use-cases, enabling framework independence. Next, I focused on developing pipelines that allowed for modularity and were well-suited for configuration files, which users would primarily use to run the models. I also worked on the distribution and hyper-parameter search to ensure efficient training of models in a distributed fashion. Lastly, I implemented a flexible logging structure that allowed multiple loggers to be used simultaneously during computations.

3. Pipelining

To ensure our system is adaptable to various use cases and applications, we should prioritize designing it with flexibility in mind. This means incorporating modularity and providing users with an easy way to develop their own components and integrate them into the framework. Interfaces play a crucial role in defining the general structure that components inherit from. In this case, the Executable interface allows components to have functions such as run, setup, and init.

Developing a new component is as simple as inheriting from the interface and implementing the desired functionality. This approach is already supported by mainstream frameworks like TensorFlow and PyTorch, where the implementation of classes such as trainer, preprocessor, and loggers are readily available. By abstracting the implementation details, as shown in Code 1, the interfaces remain framework-independent. This abstraction enables the creation of components that can unify the workings of different frameworks for the users.

```

Class
Executable(metaclass=ABCMeta):
    @abstractmethod
    def execute(self, args):
        pass

    @abstractmethod
    def setup(self, args):
        pass

class Executor(Executable):
    @abstractmethod
    def execute(self, pipeline):
        pass

    @abstractmethod
    def setup(self, pipeline):
        pass
    
```

Code 1: Examples of interface Executable and it's Executor abstract class.

In order to run efficiently developed components, pipelines were introduced. Development of pipelines was inspired by the frameworks that already work with them, that is Sklearn, or TensorFlow TFX pipelines, as in Figure 5, that are used in industry. Pipelines simply execute the components in the sequential manner passing the data through components which modify them internally.

Figure 5: Illustration of pipeline by TensorFlow TFX [Google, [link](#)].

The advantages of this approach are as follows:

1. **Checkpointing:** This approach allows for saving checkpoints, which is beneficial in cases where the pipeline crashes. By restoring the pipeline from the last working component, it saves time and energy during execution.
2. **Configurability:** Each component in the pipeline is configurable, simplifying the setup process. High-level users can easily edit the parameters of the pipeline components without needing to understand the underlying logic.
3. **Modularity:** The components can be stacked together in various ways, providing flexibility in terms of the information available during execution and model training.

To implement these advantages, an executor was introduced. This executor executes and sets up the components in a sequential manner. The implementation of the executor can be found in Code 2.

One useful feature is that the arguments can be passed down the pipeline. This allows for passing information from one component to another. For example, if a component down the pipeline requires information from a previous component, it can be passed down through the setup function. A practical use case for passing information is time management. When the pipeline starts, a folder is created, and the time is logged. Each component needs to have knowledge of the same time and folder structure, which can be achieved through the setup function.

```
class LocalExecutor(Executor):
    def __init__(self, pipeline, class_dict):
        # Create parser for the pipeline (ordered)
        pipe_parser = ArgumentParser()
        for k, v in class_dict.items():
            pipe_parser.add_subclass_arguments(v, k)

        # Parse, Instantiate pipe
        if type(pipeline) == str:
            parsed = parse_pipe_config(pipeline, pipe_parser)
        elif type(pipeline) == dict:
            parsed = pipe_parser.parse_object(pipeline)
        else:
            raise "Type of pipeline is not supported"

        pipe = pipe_parser.instantiate_classes(parsed)
        # Make pipe as a list
        self.pipe = [getattr(pipe, arg) for arg in vars(pipe)]

    def execute(self, args):
        for executable in self.pipe:
            args = executable.execute(args)

    def setup(self, args):
        for executable in self.pipe:
            args = executable.setup(args)
```

Code 2: Concrete implementation of the Local Executor in Python.

4. Distribution

Neural networks, a popular approach in the field of machine learning, are commonly used for discovering hidden patterns in data and making inferences. However, deep neural networks often require a large amount of data, creating challenges in terms of both storage and computational efficiency. With datasets that can reach tens or thousands of gigabytes, it is not feasible for them to fit into the memory of a single device, and a single GPU or CPU may not be sufficient for processing such large models and datasets.

Distributed computing offers a possible solution to these problems. A computer consists of a Central Processing Unit (CPU) with multiple cores, and each core contains threads that can work on different tasks. This allows for parallelization, where multiple GPUs or CPUs can be introduced to efficiently process large datasets. However, effective communication between these devices is essential for transferring data and minimizing overhead.

In the context of machine learning, GPUs are commonly used due to their ability to provide massive parallelization compared to CPUs. But what if one GPU is not enough? To take advantage of multiple GPUs or even computers with multiple GPUs, it is necessary to establish effective communication and distribute the training of models across these devices. Modern machine learning frameworks offer various methods for achieving distribution, with the goal of providing a unified approach that is easy for users to work with. This saves time and reduces issues when developing code, as it allows for a consistent way of distributing computations. In our case, we aim to develop Distributed Trainers for TensorFlow and Pytorch and unify them through configuration files, enabling seamless distribution of model training across multiple GPUs or computers.

a. Inside Node

To distribute computation, we can leverage the resources within a node, such as CPUs or GPUs. Our objective is to evenly distribute the training procedure across these resources. This can be achieved by dividing the dataset and distributing it across the GPUs. Additionally, the model is also distributed. During training, the models are trained independently and updated through gradients sent to a master node. The master node controls and updates the model, which is then distributed back to the GPUs. This distributed approach results in a significant speedup in training the model.

Figure 6: Illustration of distribution inside node [Google, [link](#)].

The `DistributedTrainer` module has been specifically designed to facilitate the distribution of training. By inheriting from `DistributedTrainer`, users can effortlessly define their own trainers and models. They can leverage the built-in distributed training function to distribute their training process seamlessly, without having to understand the intricacies of distribution. Internally, `DistributedTrainer` harnesses the power of TensorFlow's distributed strategies to execute models within scopes that enable distribution across nodes.

b. Outside Node

The distribution of computational nodes outside the network has become more complex. In recent times, we have access to several clusters that offer multiple computational nodes. The basic principle of computation remains the same as the inside nodes, but we now introduce an additional layer of distribution across multiple nodes, as shown in Figure 7. For instance, when it comes to model training, we need to distribute the dataset across multiple resources, splitting it accordingly. However, there is a more efficient and intuitive method for utilizing multiple nodes in training, known as hyperparameter search.

Figure 7: Illustration of outside distribution, between multiple nodes [NVIDIA, [link](#)].

5. Parameter search

Neural networks are highly sensitive to initial parameters, including the learning rate. With the increasing complexity of optimizers, users now need to select even more parameters, making the job more challenging. Finding an optimal set of parameters is not straightforward and often requires trial and error. To tackle this issue, researchers have explored parameter spaces to find feasible solutions.

One common approach is grid search, where a 2D grid is created using two initialization parameters. The model is then trained and tested for each point on the grid, and the performance metric is used to compare and select the best models. However, grid search can be time-consuming and inefficient as it does not consider dead ends. For instance, if a certain parameter consistently decreases accuracy, further exploration of that parameter value becomes unnecessary.

Fortunately, there are now frameworks available that offer better ways to explore parameter spaces. One such framework is Ray, a Python framework designed for distributed exploration and tuning of models. Ray makes it possible to distribute the exploration process across multiple nodes, enhancing efficiency. By providing a dictionary of parameters and their ranges, Ray distributes configurations to different nodes, which then train and evaluate models. Only configurations with good performance are further explored, similar to a tree search where branches with poor values are not pursued. This enables effective and distributed exploration of the parameter space.

To achieve outside node distribution, the `RayExecutor` serves as a wrapper for Ray and executes tasks on each worker `LocalExecutor`. This allows for flexible configuration not only of training but also of the entire pipeline. Although the `DistributedTrainer` can theoretically utilize multiple nodes for training large models, this is beyond the scope of the current project. However, users can specify resource allocations for each trainer to strike an optimal balance between parameter search and model training.

Figure 8: Illustration of Grid search (Left) [YourDataTeacher, [link](#)] and internal workflow of Ray (Right) [Ray, [link](#)].

In general, the pipeline is configured and executed on each node separately, advantage is that not only the training is configurable, but also the whole pipeline. For large models, the `DistributedTrainer` could theoretically use multiple nodes, not only one, and achieve even faster training, but that is not the scope of the project. Optimally, the user could then specify the resource allocations for each trainer to achieve optimal balance between parameter search and model training.

6. Future directions

The base version of the system underwent several improvements. These enhancements included the introduction of abstraction to improve the generalizability of the execution pipeline. Additionally, configurations were implemented to enable users to work independently from specific frameworks, making the model training process more efficient. Distribution was achieved through both inside and outside nodes, although further exploration is needed to incorporate multiple nodes for parameter distribution. Furthermore, a logging structure was implemented to allow for simultaneous logging into multiple systems.

To validate the effectiveness of the improved framework, new use cases were integrated. This included the integration of cyclone detection, both in its pipelined and simplified versions, with distribution capabilities. Additionally, CycleGAN was integrated into the backend to test the implementation on more complex models. The distribution functionality was also tested using multiple GPUs, as depicted in Figure 9, to evaluate the performance per epoch. The results show promising scalability, with nearly linear scaling observed. Overall, the improvements made to the system have showcased its potential for tackling complex problems and have provided valuable insights into their underlying complexity.

Figure 9: Comparison of epoch time Scaling (Left) and Efficiency (Right) during runtime

Figure 10: Comparison of pipeline time Scaling (Left) and Efficiency (Right) during runtime.

The scaling behaviour of the entire pipeline is a problem. One reason for the lack of linear scaling is the small dataset. Using multiple GPUs for a small dataset result in communication overload and significantly increases training time. To solve this problem, it is essential to measure the batch size, sample size, and dataset, and allocate resources (such as GPUs) accordingly to optimize time efficiency. This is a challenging problem that needs to be addressed in the future.

There are several future directions for improvement. First, the logging system should be unified and accessible through a single webpage for easier monitoring. Additionally, the entire pipeline could be visualized and executed using the popular Kubernetes framework. Another potential improvement is to expand the capabilities of the `DistributedTrainer` to enable distribution not only within nodes but also across nodes.

In summary, these improvements aim to enhance the generalizability and ease of development for new use-cases in a distributed fashion. The out-of-the-box distribution feature provides users with flexibility to train models in parallel and explore the parameter space of the pipelines. Furthermore, configuring the pipelines becomes easier as the user can work solely with the configuration file. These improvements offer a potential direction for solving the problem of Digital Twins for Scientific Applications.

Figure 11: Illustration of inheritance tree, together with concrete implementations of `DistributedTrainer`, `Local` and `Ray` Executors.

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